

Financial fragility and financial knowledge during the COVID-19 crisis

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Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic had a dramatic impact on individuals' well-being, stressing the need for an in-depth analysis of the factors shaping resilience to unexpected shocks, to identify vulnerable groups and define targeted relief programs (Clark et al., 2021; Clark and Mitchell, 2022).

In this study, we investigate the determinants of financial fragility in Italy during the COVID-19 crisis and focus on the role of financial knowledge. We show that individuals with higher levels of knowledge are significantly less financially fragile and provide evidence of significant heterogeneity in the impact of financial knowledge on fragility.

Methods

We use longitudinal data from the "Covid-19 Emergency: Italians between fragility and financial resilience" survey, carried out by the Italian Committee for the Planning and Coordination of Financial Education Activities and Doxa.

Following Lusardi et al. (2011), we classify as financially fragile respondents who are unable to come up with an unexpected €2,000 expense within one month. A financial knowledge score is defined from a factor analysis on questions related to six basic financial concepts.

We employ a correlated random-effects approach for unbalanced panels (CREU) and specify a panel probit model with one continuous endogenous regressor (Bates et al., 2022).

Results

Our findings indicate that more financially knowledgeable individuals are less susceptible to financial fragility. This result holds true even after controlling for pre-pandemic financial resilience and is robust to the

estimation method, sample, and definition of financial knowledge considered.

The impact of financial knowledge on financial fragility is heterogeneous across subgroups and is more beneficial for women and for individuals more severely hit by the pandemic, with lower incomes and lower pre-pandemic financial resilience.

These findings suggest that targeted public support measures and financial education programs can be effective in strengthening individuals' ability to withstand unexpected shocks.

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